

SANITARY CONDITIONS AND HEALTH STATUS OF FEMALE STUDENTS IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES A STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA, NSUKKA

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Abstract

This research work embarked upon in ascertaining the sanitary conditions of female student hostels and way to improve their health status using University of Nigeria Nsukka as area of study. A sample survey design was applied for the study. Systematic random method, purposive and availability sampling were used to select 263 students. An ordered questionnaire served for collection of data. Quantitative method of analysis was adopted to ascertain the sanitary conditions affecting students' health status. Explanatory statistics such as frequency and percentage was employed for the data presentation and analysis while chi-square statistics was used for testing of hypotheses. Results from the research indicates that the sanitary conditions in hostels are bad, and it affects the students' health status in a negative way; the factors that promote bad sanitary conditions of the hostel were the non-challant attitude of hostel cleaners towards the maintenance of sanitary facilities, inadequate number of toilets and bathrooms for the students, over population of students in the hostel and lack of maintenance of facilities. The negative effects of poor sanitation condition on the health statuses of students make them sick and unable to study, and make the environment smelly and unconducive for learning. The study therefore recommends that the school management should provide adequate facilities that will enable their workers or cleaners to do their work effectively, the school management should make a policy that will guide the hostel based on sanitation and fumigating the hostel environment.

Keywords: Sanitation, Hostel Sanitation Practices, Health Status, Female Undergraduate, Universities, Hostel Workers.

INTRODUCTION

Sanitation is an important aspect of human well-being; good sanitation improves one's health, extends life spans and makes the environment a conducive place to live in. It is practiced in order to promote hygiene and prevent disease among people through adequate facilities. According to Ikhioya (2018) sanitation refers to "a process whereby people demand, effect, and sustains a hygienic and healthy environment for them by erecting barriers to prevent the transmission of agents of diseases". The implementation of sanitation in hostels is very poor especially in female hostels. Sanitation as a global development priority, the subject of Sustainable Development Goal 6., the estimate in

2017 by the Joint Monitoring Programme (JMP) states that 4.5 billion people currently do not have safely managed sanitation. Lack of access to sanitation has an impact not only on public health but also on human dignity and personal safety (WHO/UNICEF, 2017). In all undergraduate hostels including UNN, there are cleaners whose duty are to clean the hostels environment both inside and outside environment but unfortunately their duty is not adequate enough especially in female hostels.

Ademiluyi & Odugbesan (2013), indicated that “Nigeria University hostels, adequate sanitation practices have not been ensured. They are characterized by lack of basic amenities and poor Sanitation habits”. Good health determines the student ability to read, attend classes and prepare for an examination and write well in an exam which is the primary aim of why we are in school.

According to World Health Organization (WHO 2018), health is a complete state of physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. In a study carried out by Anamali, Amadi, Okereke, Azuamah & Amadi (2019) found out that the hostel sanitation facilities available in Federal University of Technology Owerri, students' hostels are refuse waste bin, toilet, water, hand washing and drainage system among others. Also in UNN, many strategies were implemented to improve sanitation they include, provision of neat water, each hostel has up to four to five taps built at the frontage. These taps provide neat water sometimes on daily basis. This helps both the students and cleaners carry out their sanitation practice sweeping and mopping of the hostels by the cleaners, periodic cutting of grasses around the hostel environment by the school authority, monthly hostel sanitation by the students in the hostels. These are not adequate in hostel sanitation. Many studies has been carried out on the inadequate sanitation in hostels, Kabir, Roy, Begum, Kabir & Miah (2021) noted that the sanitation and hygiene practices of the students were remarkably low in Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh. For Igudia, Agbonifoh and Omobude-Idiado (2019) “Sanitation practices among undergraduate students in the University of Benin are low, age and gender influence sanitation practices”. University campuses are accepted as living laboratories with practical learning (Berchin et al., 2017).

The adoption of separate waste collection (SWC) within the university campus has great potential for adoption in general society and larger sectors, by providing a synergistic effect (Adeniran et al., 2017). In a study that assessed the level of environmental sanitation among students on the University grounds of the University of Ghana, be revealed environmental sanitation and management in the university were poor. Accommodation and sanitary facilities in the halls of residence were also found to be inadequate. In another study conducted in Ghana, factors such as absenteeism of labourers, lack of water, cleaning and refuse disposal materials contributed to sanitation problems in students' hostels at Accra Technical University (Mensah et al, 2017). University of Nigeria, Nsukka is characterized by overpopulation which is not accomplished by a corresponding increase in the sanitary facilities and services. (Daramola, 2012). Prah (2018) conducted a study at University of Cape Coast, Ghana,

and found out that most halls were overcrowded with insufficient toilets and wash rooms for students, accommodation and sanitation facilities in the halls were found to be inadequate despite some expansions in toilets and wash rooms. Availability of soaps and anal cleaning materials was found to be inadequate.

Some factors constitute as waste generator in school hostels such as: water sachets, pieces of paper, plastics of different types and broken furniture, used sanitary pads, students urinating around the hostels and students defecating in polythene bags. (Vivienne, 2014).

The UN General Assembly in 2010, noted that access to safe and clean drinking water and sanitation are human rights, and called for international efforts to help countries to provide safe, clean, accessible and affordable drinking water and sanitation (WHO, 2021). Students who reside in the hotel can be said to be the major waste generators. They have nonchalant attitude towards cleanliness of their environment. This may be because of ego, family training or the mindset they have towards that environment. Most students believe it is the duty of the cleaners to clean hostels environment and with that they do not part take or even care to take care of their environment. Even with these cleaners the environment is still not well kept because these cleaners are poorly supervised and underpaid so most of them have a nonchalant attitude to their work. With all these problems, this study aims to access the sanitary conditions and health status of female students in the hostel and also to proffer ways of improving health of the students in the area of study.

Statement of the Problem

Inadequate sanitation in hostels has been a growing concern for a long time in many hostels especially in developing countries like Nigeria. World Health Organization (2021) pointed out that “approximately 2 billion people still do not have basic sanitation facilities such as toilets or latrines. Of these, 673 million still defecate in the open, for example in street gutters, behind bushes or into open bodies of water. At least 10% of the world’s population is thought to consume food irrigated by wastewater”. Poor sanitation is one of the most pervasive and serious issues that denies students of their vital health, education, social and economic progress. WHO (2021) also stated that, Inadequate sanitation is estimated to cause 432 000 diarrheal deaths annually and is a major factor in several neglected tropical diseases, including intestinal worms, schistosomiasis and trachoma.

Results from study of quantitative research had demonstrated that students in different universities in Nigeria have suffered from inadequate sanitations in hostels which causes negative outcome to the students health. Nwobi (2022) carried out a study which examined the hostel sanitation practices for improved health status among undergraduate students in universities in Enugu State, result from the study shows that the hostel sanitation practices of majority of the undergraduates in university hostels are poor and unhygienic. Undergraduates are aware of the importance of practicing proper hostel sanitation and the implication it has on their health status. Also Okpala, Iheanacho,

Okoronkwo & Stephen (2014) research on student's perception of environmental sanitation in female hostels in Nigerian University showed that students felt that the sanitary condition of their hostels was poor because most of the basic elements of environmental health were inadequate, such as safe water and basic sanitation. Factors perceived to promote good environmental sanitation were identified as: creation of awareness, inclusion of environmental sanitation in the school curriculum, and those that are responsible for poor environmental sanitation: improper refuse disposal, inadequate personnel. Results also showed that although many students could identify diseases associated with environmental sanitation, only about half of them (54%) agreed that typhoid fever is one of such diseases.

The implication of this for the health of the population is glaring since typhoid fever has become endemic in Nigeria. There is need for improvement in the environmental sanitation of the country and proper enlightenment among university students as their knowledge will positively affect their life styles. Ogundele (2021), researched on Impact of hostel sanitation practices on the health of male undergraduates in University of Lagos. Analysis of data from the study revealed that there is significant perceived effect of sanitation on physical health of undergraduates in male hostels of University of Lagos, there is significant influence of sanitation practice on behavioral health of undergraduates in male hostels in University of Lagos, practice of sanitation is significantly beneficial on psychological health of undergraduates in male hostels in University of Lagos.

This study hereby recommended that the University of Lagos Medical Centre in conjunction with the University of Lagos Counseling Unit should embark on sensitization exercise. This will bring to the limelight the issues of sanitation and its impact on health status among the hostel dwellers. The University of Lagos Management should provide basic sanitary facilities like adequate water supply, waste bins, brooms etc. These will empower the students in practicing good environmental sanitation, The mandatory Thursday sanitation exercises should be continued and enforcement officers should be mandated to go round inspecting the university community to ensure compliance.

Poor sanitation is highly prevalent in Nigeria universities mainly due to the problem of inadequate facilities, attitude of hostel cleaners and students. Some challenges affecting hostel sanitation practices among undergraduates for improved health status in hostels are inadequate toilets in the hostel, Poor drainage system in the hostel, Absenteeism of hostel cleaners, Inadequate water supply in the hostel among others (Nwobi 2022). Many researchers have explored the issues of sanitation in University hostels. For instance, Nwadike et al (2017), kabir et al (2021), Nwobi (2022) all wrote on environmental sanitation education which looked at the issues pertaining to provision and deficiencies of facilities and services. Despite all these researches, female students hostels are still not in good condition hence this research intend to explore strategies to improve sanitary conditions in female hostels in UNN

Objectives of Study

The study aimed to determine whether:

- i. Hostel workers who engage in hostel cleaning are more likely to keep the hostel clean than female students in University of Nigeria Nsukka
- ii. Hostels with facilities are more likely to have high level of sanitation practices than those with low facilities in University of Nigeria Nsukka
- iii. Female students are more likely to have the negative health effect of poor sanitation practices than hostel workers in University of Nigeria Nsukka
- iv. Proffer possible strategies to improve hostel sanitation practices in female hostels in University of Nigeria Nsukka

LITERATURE REVIEW

Maintaining high standard of hygiene is of great important in hostels especially female hostels considering their reproductive systems. As pointed out by Araral, Yoshino, and Seetha Ram (2019), “the benefits of sanitation infrastructure... include reductions in diarrhea, cholera, typhoid, dysentery, and hepatitis, along with an increase in local economic development, a reduction in groundwater contamination, improvement in the recharge status of nearby aquifers, and economic benefits, such as the reuse of treated water for agriculture and/or industrial purposes and in terms of waste-to-energy benefits.” Diarrhea, a main cause of malnutrition and stunted growth in children, can be reduced through adequate sanitation (WHO, 2017). Now, the United Nations’ Sustainable Development goal (SDG) is for everyone to have “adequate and equitable” sanitation and basic hygiene for all by 2030. (SDG 6, 2017). United Nations (2017), defined Basic sanitation as “having access to facilities for the safe disposal of human waste (feces and urine), as well as having the ability to maintain hygienic conditions, through services such as garbage collection, industrial/hazardous waste management, and wastewater treatment and disposal”. Sanitation is also referred to as the provision of facilities and services for the safe disposal of human urine and feces (WHO, 2018).

Preventing human contact with faces is part of sanitation, as is hand washing with soap. Sanitation systems aim to protect human health by providing a clean environment that will stop the transmission of diseases, especially through the fecal-oral route (Susana, 2018). According to (UNICEF and WHO, 2020), The SDGs challenge Member States to achieve three progressively ambitious targets with respect to household sanitation:

1. Eliminating open defecation: this is explicitly mentioned in the target text, and is particularly relevant to a small number of high-burden countries.
2. Achieve worldwide right to use vital hygiene services: most countries aim to provide at least a vital stage of hygiene services to their entire populations within the SDG period.

3. Achieving entire availability to securely managed sanitation delivery: for many countries reaching universal coverage with safely managed sanitation by 2030 is not a realistic target, but milestones and interim targets can still be set. Even for high- and middle-income countries, it is a challenge to reach entire populations with sanitation services that ensure proper management of excreta along the entire sanitation chain.

A sanitation system includes the capture, storage, transport, treatment and disposal or reuse of human excreta and wastewater (Gates Foundation, 2020). Reuse activities within the sanitation system may focus on energy or untreated substances contained in human waste and fitter away water. This is referred to as the “sanitation value chain” or “sanitation economy” (Paranipe, 2017). The people in charge of clean up, operations on sanitation expertise all time in cleanliness sequence are called “sanitation workers” (World Bank, International Labour Organization, WaterAids & WHO, 2019). Sanitation can include either individual hygiene or general cleanliness. Individual sanitation work can include managing disposals, cleaning household rest room, and managing domestic waste. General sanitation work can involve garbage collection, transfer and treatment (municipal solid waste management), cleaning drains, streets, schools, trains, public spaces, community toilets and public toilets, sewers, operating sewage treatment plants, etc (PRIA, 2019).

According to Sahana (2023), there are different types of sanitation which the government have encouraged communities to engage in either one or more of these types in other to have a good sanitation practice, they includes:

Basic sanitation that is, the application of better sanitary equipments meant only for a particular household, container-based sanitation system in which toilets collect human waste in removable and lockable containers that are transported to treatment facilities, community organized total sanitation which is a method mainly used in developing countries to improve sanitary and hygienic practices in a community, dry disinfection system that uses a dry, drain less toilet to move excreta, ecological sanitation approach that aims to safely reuse excreta in agriculture, emergency sanitation which is the management and technical processes required to provide sanitary equipments in emergency situations and environmental hygiene which involves controlling environmental factors associated with the transmission of disease.

Every day, over 800 children under the age of five die from diarrhea-related infections that could be prevented if they had their way to pure water, cleanliness, and sanitation. Furthermore, diarrhea leads to loss of appetite in children, thus resulting in malnutrition (Humanitarian Global 2022).

Adequate sanitation is a primary protective barrier to fecal-oral disease transmission, proven sanitation intervention can reduce the incidence of diarrhea by 30 to 10 percent (Cairn cross, Hunt, Boisson, Boston, Curtis, Fung & Schmidt, 2020). Poor sanitation is linked to early childhood stunting and delayed mental and physical development, both of

which can have significant lifelong effects (Merchant, Jones, Kiure, Kipka, Fitz Maurice, Herrera & Fawzi, 2013).

According to Seetharam, &Kusha, (2015) “the inability to link sanitation with other sanitation issues (e.g. solid waste, storm water management), poor public perception, inadequate consideration of the social, cultural, political and economic factors into sanitation projects, the omission of potential actors, the assumption to implement a single technology that fits to all state of affairs, and the absence of multi-step process of sanitation from waste generation to disposal are key challenges high standard of hygiene. This results in overcrowding, slums, and squatter settlements in different parts of an urban area”.

The following can be said to be the factors affecting sanitation in the hostels: Disobedience to sanitary rules and regulations, overcrowding, squatting, irregular/inadequate water supply, inadequate facilities and lack of maintenance of facilities by the management and students. Though various sanitation practices are being carried out in the hostels to help improve the sanitation level of the hostels, like provision of neat water, sweeping and mopping of the hostels by the cleaners, periodic cutting of grasses around the hostel environment by the school authority: The school authority periodically pays workers to cut the grasses around the hostels and also around the school environment and monthly hostel sanitation by the students in the hostels.

Research Hypotheses

- 1) Over population in the female hostels affects the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.
- 2) Inadequate provision of sanitation facilities affects the health status of students residing in University of Nigeria Nsukka female hostels.
- 3) The Non-chalant attitude towards maintenance of available facilities contributes to the poor sanitary state of the female hostels in University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted systems theory (Haralambos & Holborn 2015) and environmental justice theory (Schlosberg 2007). These theories seems to be the most appropriate to be employed. According to system theory, society is a system made up of interrelated parts which must function together for the society to survive. There is also some degree of intervention between the parts of the society. Order and stability are essential for maintaining social systems and are largely provided by value consensus. When the major value is expressed in the various parts of the social structure such as: the family, the economy, the education and political system, those parts will be integrated and there would be order and stability.

Sanitation is therefore a value which all members of a society would always agree on. In the family, one learns from childhood the significance of excellent hygiene and sanitary activities. The educational system carries on from where the family institution stopped.

Those systems expose the child to other aspects of hygiene and sanitation which he/she is not aware of. The economic system also encourages good sanitation habits amongst households, students and human in general by producing machines and products that aid sanitation, for example: washing machine, dish washer, detergent, disinfectants, incinerators etc. Environmental justice theory as a social movement address environmental injustice, which occurs when poor or marginalized communities are harmed by hazardous waste, resource extraction, and other land uses from which they do not benefit. The relevance of the theory to the study was that it noted the increase in environmental problems and benefits due to our environmental practices; it also establishes the importance of communities and individuals and in the case of this study, student's contribution towards the protection and preservation of the environment. The health status of students living in the hostel should be put into uttermost consideration. The school authority should endeavor to improve the health and living standards of the students living in school hostels by providing and ensuring a good sanitation practice amongst students. This can be done through the Department for Students' Affairs. These sanitation practices should be made into laws, which are then enforced through appropriate authorities such as the hall supervisors, hall portals and the hall governors. These practices should include all unit of the hostel, both the hostel cleaners and the students. This when achieved will go a long way in promoting the sanitation conditions of the hostels, thereby promoting good health conditions of the students.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study adopted cross sectional survey design.

Research Area

This research was conducted in University of Nigeria Nsukka campus, Enugu state, Nigeria. The University of Nigeria Nsukka campus has about nine (9) faculties and also sixty-four departments and other units and sub-departments.

Study Population

The population of the study is students residing in all female hostels in University of Nigeria Nsukka, there are fourteen female hostels within the campus. These fourteen hostels are Isa Kaita, Okeke, Akintola, Akpabio, Balewa, Okpara, Eyo-Ita, Bello, Awolowo, Ajah Nwachukwu, Mary Slessor, Presidential and Nkrumah hostel and E-Block. Below is the breakdown of the population of students in each hostel as gotten from the Student Affairs Department, University of Nigeria, Nsukka: Mary Slessor Hall: 257 bed spaces Bello Hall: 364 bed spaces Aja Nwachukwu Hall: 364 bed spaces Balewa Hall: 357 bed spaces Okpara Hall: 354 bed spaces Eyo-Ita Hall: 364 bed spaces Awolowo Hall: 455 bed spaces Akintola Hall: 364 bed spaces Akpabio Hall: 367 bed spaces Isa kaita Hall: 388 bed spaces

Okeke Hall: 455 bed spaces Nkrumah Hall: 652 bed spaces Presidential Hall: 224 bed spaces E- Block: 106 bed spaces

Total number of legal occupants residing in the hostels = 5,070 students.

Scope of the Study

This research work focused on the sanitation practices carried out in all the female hostels in University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus. The population comprises a total of 5,070 according to Student Affairs Department, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Sample Size

The Cochran (1963) formula was used to determine the study sample size (263 respondents), assuming a 95% of reliability point, .05% edge of inaccuracy and 50% fraction.

Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + N)(e)^2}$$

n= Number of subjects to be drawn from the population (sample size).

N= Population figure.

e= Level of precision (tolerance error margin) 95% confidence level and e= 0.06 are assumed.

1= Unity (always constant in value).

Substituting the formula we have:

$$n = 5070 / (1 + 5070(0.06)^2)$$

$$n = 5070 / (1 + 5070(0.0036))$$

$$n = 5070 / 1 + 18.252$$

$$n = 5070 / 19.252$$

$$n = 263.34$$

Therefore, the sample size will be 263

Sampling Techniques

A multistage sampling technique comprising systematic random sampling, purposive sampling and availability sampling. Out of the fourteen (14) female undergraduate hostels, systematic sampling was used to select seven (7) hostels which are: Balewa Hall, Okpara Hall, Akintola Hall, Akpabio Hall, Bello Hall, Eyo-Ita Hall and Mary Slessor Hall. From the selected hostels, purposive sampling was applied to share 30 questionnaires to

students in hostels near to each other. In order to get the required sample size, availability sampling was used.

Data Collection and analysis

This study employed a quantitative method of data collection using a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed with closed and open- ended questions with section A assessing the socio- demographic characteristics of the respondents and section B dealing with the main research issues. Information collected be analyze using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 22) and the results were presented Descriptive statistics like frequency distribution tables and percentages were used to explain the information gathered from the respondents. The hypothesis was tested using Chi Square (X^2) method of statistical analysis

RESULTS

Two hundred and sixty-three (263) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. Two hundred and fifty (250) copies of the questionnaire were correctly completed and returned. Therefore, this analysis is based on two hundred and fifty (250) returned copies of the questionnaire.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by socio-demographic variables: age, level of study and hostel

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Age		
15- 19 years	62	24.8
20-24 years	146	58.4
25- 29years	42	16.8
30 years and above	-	-
Total	250	100
Level of study		
First year	38	15.2
Second year	44	17.6
Third year	99	39.6
Fourth year	47	18.8
Other years	22	8.8
Total	250	100
Hostel		
Eyo- Ita	35	14.0
Balewa	40	16.0
Okpara	40	16.0
Bello	30	12.0
Akintola	30	12.0
Akpabio	42	16.8
Mary Slessor	33	16.5
Total	250	100

Source: *Field work, 2024*

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to age, level of study and hostel. The response on age shows that 24.8% of the respondents were within the age range of 15 - 19years, 58.4% were within the age range of 20 - 24years, 16.8% were within the age range of 25 - 29years while none of the respondent fall between 30years and above. This reveals that the highest proportion of the respondents were within the age range of 20 - 24years.

For the level of study of the respondents, the data indicated that 15.2% of the respondents were 100 level students, 17.6% were 200 level students, 39.6% were 300 level students, 18.8% were 400 level students while 8.8% were students in other years like 500 level. This reveals that majority of the respondents were 300 level students.

Lastly, for hostel of residence, the response reveals that 14% of the respondents stay in Eyo-lta hostel, 16% stay in Balewa hostel, 16% stay in Okpara hostel, 12% stay in Bello hostel, 12% stay in Akintola, 16.8% stay in Akpabio while 16.5% stay in Mary Slessor. This data shows that there is almost an equal distribution of the respondents according to hostel of residence.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by their awareness of sanitation practices carried out in their hostel

Are you aware of any sanitation practice carried out in the hostel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	211	84.4
No	39	15.6
Total	250	100.0

Source: *Field work, 2024*

This table shows the percentage distribution of the respondents by their awareness of the sanitation practices carried out in their hostel. From the table above, 84.4% are aware of the practices carried out while 15.6% are not aware. From the table, majority of the respondents are aware of the sanitation practices carried out in their hostel

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by their views on how often the common areas are cleaned in their hostel

How often are the common areas cleaned in the hostels	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Daily	87	34.8
Weekly	100	40
Monthly	35	17.4
Never	28	11.2
Total	250	100.0

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Table 3 shows the percentage distribution of respondents on their views on how often the common areas are cleaned in their hostel. From the table above, 34.8% of the respondents indicated daily, while 40%, 14%, 11.2% indicated weekly, monthly and never

respectively. From the data presented, it could be seen that majority of the respondents indicated that the common areas in the hostel are cleaned Daily

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by their views on whether over population affects the sanitary conditions in the hostel

Does over population in the hostel affect the sanitary conditions of students in the hostel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	180	72
No	70	28
Total	250	100.0

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Table 4 shows the percentage distribution of the respondents by their views on whether over population affects the sanitary conditions in the hostel. From the table above, 72% indicated Yes, while 28% indicated No. From the data presented, it could be seen that majority of the respondents indicated Yes.

Table 5: Percentage distribution of the respondents by whether they have ever contacted a communicable disease while staying in the hostel

Ever contacted a communicable disease while staying in the hostel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	110	44
No	96	38.4
Not sure	44	17.6
Total	250	100.0

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the respondents by whether they have ever contacted a communicable disease while staying in the hostel. From the responses, 44% of the respondents indicated Yes, 38.4% indicated No, while 17.6% indicated Not sure. From the responses, it could be seen that majority of the respondents indicated Yes.

Table 6: Percentage distribution of the respondents by whether they have ever missed classes or academic activities due to health issues related to hostel sanitation

Hostel sanitation conditions influence health status of students in the hostel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	173	69.2
No	77	30.8
Total	250	100.0

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Table 6 shows the percentage distribution of the respondents by their views on whether sanitation conditions influence their health status. From the responses, 69.2% of the respondents indicated Yes, while 30.8% indicated No. From the table, it could be seen that majority of the respondents indicated Yes.

Table 7: Distribution of the respondents by their views on whether there is enough cleaning supplies provided in the hostel

Adequate provision of cleaning of cleaning supplies in hostels	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	76	30.4
No	174	69.6
Total	250	100.0

Table 7 shows the percentage distribution of respondents by their views on whether there is enough cleaning supplies provided. The response shows that 30.4% of the respondents indicated Yes while 69.6% of the respondents indicated No. From the data presented, majority of the respondents indicated No, that not enough cleaning supplies are provided.

Table 8: Percentage distribution of the respondents by their views on whether the Nonchallant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities contributes to the poor sanitary state in the hostel

The non- challant attitude towards maintenance of available facilities contribute to the poor sanitation state of hostel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	150	60
No	100	40
Total	250	100.0

Table 8 shows the percentage distribution of the respondents by their views on whether the Nonchallant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities contributes to the poor sanitary state of the hostel. From the responses, 60% of the respondents indicated Yes, while 40% of the respondents indicated No. From the data above, it could be seen that majority of the respondents indicated Yes.

Test of Hypotheses

Substantive hypothesis: Over population in the female hostels affects the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.

Null hypothesis: Over population in the female hostels do not affect the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.

Table 9: Cross tabulation of table 4 & 6: Distribution of respondents on whether hostel Sanitary conditions influence health status of people in the hostel and if overpopulation affect sanitary conditions in the hostel

Hostel sanitation conditions influence status of people in the hostel	Does overpopulation affect sanitary conditions in the hostel		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	103 (55%)	20(15.5%)	123 (61.5%)
No	27 (10%)	50 (45.5%)	77 (38.5%)
Total 130 (65%)	70 (70%)	250 (100%)	

Source: Field survey, 2024 $p=0.044$ $N=250$

The table above shows that 123 (61.5%) of the respondents agreed that overpopulation affect sanitary conditions in the hostel while 77 (38.5%) noted that overpopulation does not affect sanitary conditions in the hostel.

The results from the chi square analysis shows that the p value (0.44) is less than the alpha value (.05), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis which states that Over population in the female hostels affects the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels and reject the null hypothesis which states that Over population in the female hostels does not affects the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.

Hypothesis Two

Substantive hypothesis: The inadequate provision of sanitary facilities affects the health status of students residing in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.

Null hypothesis: The inadequate provision of sanitary facilities does not affect the health stats of students residing in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.

Table 10: Cross tabulation of table 4 & 6; Distribution of respondents on whether hostel sanitary conditions influence health status of people in the hostel and if inadequate provision of sanitary facilities affects those in the hostel

Hostel sanitation conditions influence status of people in the hostel	Does inadequate provision of sanitation facilities affect student's health status		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	174 (72%)	27 (10.5%)	201 (82.5%)
No	27 (10.5%)	22 (7.5%)	49 (17.5%)
Total	201 (82%)	49 (70%)	250 (100%)

Source: *Field survey, 2024* $p= 0.011$ $N=250$

The table above shows that 201 (82%) of the respondents agreed that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities affect student's health status while 49 (17.5%) noted that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities does not affect student's health status. The results from the chi square analysis shows that the p value (0.11) is less than the alpha value (.05), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis which states that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities affect student's health status and reject the null hypothesis which states that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities does not affect student's health status.

Hypothesis Three

Substantive hypothesis: The Nonchallant attitude towards maintenance of available facilities contributes to the poor sanitary state of the female hostels in University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Null hypothesis: The Nonchallant attitude towards maintenance of available facilities does not contribute to the poor sanitary state of the female hostels in University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Table 11: Cross tabulation of table 4 & 8; Distribution of respondents on whether the non challant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities influence health status of people in the hostel and if sanitary conditions influence health status of people in the hostel

Hostel sanitation conditions influence status of people in the hostel	non challant attitude towards the maitenance sanitation conditions influence status of people in the hostel		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	176(69.5%)	23(11.5%)	199 (81%)
No	33(10.5%)	18 (8.5%)	51 (19%)
Total	199 (81%)	41 (19%)	250 (100%)

Source: *Field survey, 2024* $p= 0.002$ $N=250$

The table above shows that 199 (81%) of the respondents agreed that non challant attitude towards the maintenance sanitation conditions influence status of people in the hostel while 51 (19%) disagreed. The results from the chi square analysis shows that the p value (0.02) is less than the alpha value (.05), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

This study was embarked upon to examine sanitary conditions and health status of students in female hostels in University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The study yielded important findings showing the various views of female in hostels towards sanitary conditions of the hostels and health status of the students.

Findings from the study shows that 24.8% of the respondents were within the age range of 15 - 19years, 58.4% were within the age range of 20 - 24years, 16.8% were within the age range of 25 - 29years while non of the respondent fall between 30years and above. This reveals that the highest proportion of the respondents were within the age range of 20 - 24years. Also, the data indicated that 15.2% of the respondents were 100 level students, 17.6% were 200 level students, 39.6% were 300 level students, 18.8% were 400 level students while 8.8% were students in other years like 500 level. This reveals that majority of the respondents were 300 level students.

The study findings revealed that a great percentage of the respondents are knowledgeable of what environmental sanitation is all. The response shows that 99.2% of the respondents have knowledge of sanitation. From the responses too it was discovered that students have different ways of carrying out sanitation practices. 14% observes sanitation by sweeping, 10.8% observes sanitation by scrubbing while 12% of the respondents observe sanitation by gathering dirts.

This findings is in line with the study by WHO(2018) which defined sanitation as the provision of facilities and services for the safe disposal of human urine and faeces. It went further to state that sanitation also refers to the maintenance of hygienic conditions,

through services such as garbage and wastewater disposal (WHO2018). The study findings revealed also that all the respondents opined that there is need for environmental sanitation in the hostel as the sanitary level affects their health as indicated by 69.2% of the respondents. Supporting this findings, Susana(2018) states that sanitation systems aim to protect human health by providing a clean environment that will stop the transmission of diseases, especially through the fecal-oral route.

For example, diarrhea, a main cause of malnutrition and stunted growth in children, can be reduced through adequate sanitation (WHO, 2017). The study findings revealed that poor sanitation practices by undergraduate students exposes them to various forms of infection, and these diseases has financial implications on the students as they use available resources, mostly in the form of cash to treat themselves of these infirmities. To find its objectives and findings, the study tested 3 hypothesis.

Findings from the first hypothesis showed that above shows that 123 (61.5%) of the respondents agreed that overpopulation affect sanitary conditions in the hostel while 77 (38.5%) noted that overpopulation does not affect sanitary conditions in the hostel.

The results from the chi square analysis shows that the p value (0.44) is less than the alpha value (.05), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis which states that Over population in the female hostels affects the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels and reject the null hypothesis which states that Over population in the female hostels does not affects the sanitary conditions in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels.

Findings from the second hypothesis showed that, 201 (82%) of the respondents agreed that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities affect student's health status while 49 (17.5%) noted that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities does not affect student's health status.

The results from the chi square analysis shows that the p value (0.17) is less than the alpha value (.05), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis which states that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities affect student's health status and reject the null hypothesis which states that inadequate provision of sanitation facilities does not affect student's health status.

Findings from the third hypothesis showed that 199 (81%) of the respondents agree that the Nonchalant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities affects student's health status while 51 (19%) of the respondents indicated that Nonchalant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities does not affect student's health status.

The result from the chi square analysis shows that the p value (0.048) is less than the alpha value (0.5), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis which states that the Nonchalant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities affects student's health and reject the null hypothesis which states that the Nonchalant attitude towards the maintenance of available facilities does not affect student's health status.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study examined the hostel sanitation practices and its effects on student's health in University of Nigeria, Nsukka female hostels. The finding showed that the hostel sanitation practices in University of Nigeria, Nsukka is low which is due to the lack of enough sanitary facilities in the hostel and also students littering the hostel environment with dirt. This study agrees with that of Mensah-Kufuor and Gablah (2017) that there is an indication showing that there are sanitation problems in the institution. They pointed that students fall sick regularly due to the bad situation of the toilet causing them infections and malaria due to mosquitoes breeding in the areas of poor drainage. From their response, they pointed that lack of sanitation facilities is a major problem in the hostel as indicated by 69.6% of the respondents. Also from their responses it was noted that over population in the hostel affects the sanitary conditions in the hostel as indicated by 72% of the respondents, the Nonchallant attitude towards maintenance of available facilities was not left out as a problem too as indicated by 60% of the respondents.

Also it was noted that the poor sanitary conditions in the hostel affects students health as indicated by 69.2% of the respondents. 58.8% of the respondents indicated that they have faced health issues since staying in the hostel and this in turn affects their mental well-being as indicated by 48.4% of the respondents. This has a way of affecting students academic life by making them fall sick or miss academic activities as indicated by 42.4% of the respondents.

Conclusion

This study was embarked upon to examine the sanitary conditions and health status of female students residing in the hostel in University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Based on the findings, the study concluded that though there are sanitation facilities in the hostel but, they are not adequate and the school has not really made any effort to improve on this. It was concluded that students fall sick regularly due to the poor sanitation practices and it has a negative effects on their health. This, to a good extent affects the students both health and economic wise. In summary, it was also concluded that the hostel sanitation practices in University of Nigeria, Nsukka is low.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been made in the light of the findings from the field.

1. The school management should provide adequate facilities that will enable their workers or labourers to do their work effectively and efficiently.
2. The school management should make a policy that will guide the hostel based on sanitation.
3. Sanitation practices should not only been enforced by only the cleaners, but to every students of the hostel.

4. Fumigating the environment, provision of facilities, employing more cleaners, cannot be over-emphasized.
5. The school management should lay down and strictly implement hygiene policies as well as educate and encourage students on the need and effects for good hygiene practices on their health and the environment. All hands must be on deck to ensure a careful and good hostel sanitation practices.
6. The school management should try and renovate the toilet ends of most of these hostel in order to reduce the bad odour that comes from the hostel.

The researchers, therefore wishes to conclude that if these recommendations are implemented against poor hostel sanitation practices by students health in University of Nigeria, Nsukka; there will be improved hygiene practices and maintenance of good health among students.

Limitations of the Study

1. Financial constraint: Insufficient fund tends to impede the efficiency of the researcher in sourcing for the relevant materials, literature or information and in the process of data collection (internet, questionnaire and interview).
2. Time constraint: The researcher simultaneously engaged in this study with academic work and other extra-curriculum activities. This consequently cut down on the time devoted for the research work.

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